

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR IN
SECONDARY SCHOOL

Kuchkinov Khudaybergan Khidirovich

Teacher of Termez Institute of Agrotechnology and Innovative Development

Abstract: Issues of using Internet resources in teaching grammar of English language with application of communicative approach are described in the article. In the course of the work three sources were distinguished as the most diverse and qualitative, which were further examined with the possibility of using them in an online English lesson and lesson at school.

Key words: English language, grammar, communicative approach, Internet resources

Learning English grammar is always a difficult process to most of the English as Foreign Language (EFL) learners at secondary school level. Innovative ideas, interesting teaching materials, practicing and drilling learners for learning the English grammar should be done through fun and joyful ways. The main aim of this library study was to identify and describe examples of practical grammar instruction methods in an EFL which employed innovative methodologies. The process of the library-based research involves identifying and locating relevant information, analyzing what has been found, and then developing and expressing the ideas. The results revealed that songs and poems, music, games, and tasks can be employed as tools in the classroom. Using innovative methodologies in teaching English grammar in the classroom at the secondary schools has paved a positive way to students to learn the language meaningfully.

The most common and widely accepted technologies in second language teaching are computers and the internet. Some separate the internet and computers into two separate categories, but oftentimes the internet will be accessed in class through a computer.

Immersion and repetition are the basic tools of effective foreign language teaching. Immersion keeps you thinking in the language and focused on learning it. Repetition is vital to memorization and learning each word or phrase along with its place in speech.

Nowadays, the educational process is increasingly modernized, most schools are equipped with interactive whiteboards, teachers record grades in an electronic journal, and even in 2020, schools are faced with transition to distance learning due to the pandemic. Moreover, such scientists as David Crystal, M. Warschauer, E.V. spoke about the relevance and feasibility of using Internet technologies. Voevoda, E.Ya. Sokolova. Consequently, at present there is an increasing need to move from the traditional teaching system to the “blended learning” or “blended learning” system, i.e. an educational concept that combines traditional learning with distance and online methods. lessons. The use of Internet technologies has not only an entertaining purpose, but also contributes to the development of communication skills, independence, creativity, increasing student motivation, developing students’ basic competencies, taking into account their individual characteristics, helping to implement an activity-based approach to learning, attracting passive students to active activities in the classroom, and also contributes to the modernization of general education. Educational Internet resources contain text, graphic, audio, photo and video material on various educational topics. However, when using Internet technologies should have a developed lesson plan with the purpose, time of using the Internet (Web-based lesson) and an algorithm of actions with clear instructions [4]. It is also especially important to select in advance proven, effective websites that will meet the objectives of the lesson. In full-time schooling, in our opinion, Internet

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technologies should not be used for the entire lesson, as this may cause organizational risk, but doing a few exercises or introducing a new topic using Internet sites will help both students and teachers get used to the new space. Summarizing everything that has been said, Innovative technologies play an important role in learning, but care must be taken in selecting the correct and useful resources. We would like to draw attention to the use of some Internet technologies in teaching English grammar within the framework of a communicative approach.

It should be noted that all exercises from Internet resources should be used as part of a lesson script, and not as complete teaching units. We will consider the following resources: "National Corpus of the Russian Language" and "British National Corpus", "Wordwall", "LearningApps.org", "Superteachertools.com", "Baamboozle", "Quizizz", "Triventy", "English Media Lab", "Padlet.com", "Pixton Edu", "Printdiscuss.com", "Brainyquote.com". It is these resources that were selected because they contain completely diverse methods in teaching English grammar and are proven and effective in achieving educational goals.

With the advent of computer technology, corpus linguistics has developed greatly, resulting in the emergence of Internet sites with corpora of different languages, for example, the National Corpus of the Russian Language (NCRL) [2], with a volume of more than 600 million words, and the British National Corpus (BNC), with a volume of 100 million words. These resources can be used as search work, for example, to determine the meaning of a prefix based on examples or to find different words with the same root. You can also do comparative analysis of languages using Russian and English corpora, for example, to compare the order of words in a sentence, because in English, unlike Russian, there is a stricter word order, and a language corpus containing thousands of examples from texts of different genres, will demonstrate this perfectly. At the end of each mini-research paper, students or groups of students need to draw a conclusion or express their assumptions in English. The teacher can also use the corpus to create exercises, for example replacing affixes with ellipses and ask students to guess the word based on the text. Thus, the use of a corpus helps to interest students, present the topic in a non-standard way, and also represents one of the methods of problem-based learning.

On the Baamboozle website, the game features a variety of visual task cards and is great for reinforcing grammar topics and communication practice. Cards typically contain a graphic or animated image and a question or task at the bottom. You must answer the task or question orally, and after answering, click on the card to check. Based on this, the site can be used in a lesson as a frontal survey or by dividing the class into teams, but control student responses

Only the teacher can do this, it is not displayed on the website. You can find the grammar games you need using the search bar. When creating your own games on this resource, you can hide cards with questions under numbers for playing with teams. Students on one team choose a question and answer it. For the correct answer, points are awarded, which are calculated automatically. The site has free and paid versions. The free version includes creating your own games, four teams per game, uploading 1 MB of images, and a game with 24 questions. The advantages of the paid version include a larger number of commands and loading images, creating several games in one game, creating multiple-choice exercises, the number of questions increases to 48, and advertising is removed. This site was created by an American organization specifically for use in lessons as a warm-up before a lesson, reinforcing a topic or monitoring the mastery of a grammatical topic. This resource is completely different from the previous ones, but is not inferior in entertaining and educational forms.

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The Padlet.com service is a virtual board for collecting and storing information. As part of school English grammar teaching, the site can be used to gather information on a specific grammar topic, as a method for brainstorming on a specific topic, or for a class project assignment. The site has the following types of boards: “wall”, “canvas”, “tape”, “storyboard”, “columns”, “conversations”, “map”, “chronology”. The design of the board can be changed, the materials can be placed in different sequences, the finished board can be saved as a picture or a pdf file, which allows students to repeat the collected and covered material on a grammar topic at home. Materials for the board can serve as texts, videos, tests, documents, quizzes and other sites. Students can also comment on pinned content. The created board can be public or assigned to a specific group persons The site is available in thirty-four languages, including Russian and English, and has free and paid versions. In the free version you can create only three boards. In general, the resource “Padlet.com” has not so much an entertaining, but an educational task, it activates students to solve a problem, forms innovative thinking, and also helps students who missed a lesson to remain participants in the project or watch and try to understand the topic covered on the virtual board .

Thus, the above educational Internet resources contribute to the formation and development of language and ICT competencies, expand the possibilities of the lesson in the context of the implementation of the Federal State Educational Standard, developing various types of meta-subject educational learning for students, help create motivation and interest students in learning English, develop communication skills in working in Internet. However, undoubtedly, the Internet is an endless repository of information, and even educational sites are not always correct and suitable for conducting school lessons. Therefore, before the lesson, it is recommended to check and select the necessary material for a successful lesson.

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